

Synthesis, spectral characterization, thermal and biocidal properties of metal complexes with N-substituted sulfonamides

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Abstract : Two new Schiff base ligands formed by the condensation of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde with sulfapyridine and sulfathiazole and their metal complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, thermal studies, magnetic moment, EPR, IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, mass and electronic spectral data. Both ligands are bidentate, coordinating through azomethine nitrogen and hydroxyl oxygen after deprotonation. These compounds were screened for *in vitro* antibacterial activity against Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*), Gram-negative (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, *Klebsiella* sp.) bacterial strains and for *in vitro* antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Mucor* sp. and *Candida albicans*. The results of these studies revealed that all complexes exhibited significant to moderate antibacterial activity. All the complexes exhibit six coordinated octahedral geometry.

Keywords : Metal complexes, sulfonamides, antibacterial, antifungal.

Introduction

The field of bioinorganic chemistry, which deals with the study of role of metal complexes in biological systems, has opened a new horizon for scientific research in coordination compounds. Transition metal complexes have attracted attentions of inorganic, metallo-organic as well as bio-inorganic chemists because of their extensive applications in wide range of areas from material to biological sciences¹⁻¹⁰. Several metal complexes are known to accelerate the drug action and the efficacy of the organic therapeutic agents. The efficacy of the various organic therapeutic agents can often be enhanced upon coordination with a suitable metal ion¹¹.

Schiff bases are versatile ligands capable of forming complexes with most of the transition elements and able to stabilize transition metals in a variety of oxidation states. N-Substituted sulfonamides are the most widely used antibacterial agents in the world, mainly because of their low cost, low toxicity and excellent activity against bacterial disease¹². The substituted salicylaldehyde Schiff base derivatives were most active against the bacterial species¹³. The presence of *o*-hydroxy group has been regarded as one of the important factors which favours che-

lation to give stable six membered ring with metal. In this paper we report the synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial studies of new type of bidentate Schiff base ligands derived from 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and sulfapyridine/sulfathiazole and their metal complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II). The ligand has both oxygen and nitrogen donor sites. All compounds were thoroughly characterized by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H and ¹³C magnetic resonance (NMR), mass and ultraviolet-visible spectroscopic methods. EPR and thermogravimetric analysis were done as well.

Experimental

Material and methods :

All chemicals and reagents used were of analytical reagent grade (AR) except ethanol which was purified prior to use¹⁴. Conductance measurements were studied using Elico conductivity bridge and dip type conductivity cell. Elemental analysis was carried out with a Elemental Vario EL III model. IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets on a Shimadzu 8000 FTIR spectrophotometer in the range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹. Absorbance spectra were recorded on a Systronic spectrophotometer in the range

of 300–1000 nm. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of compounds were recorded with a Bruker Spectrospin Avance DPX-400 using TMS as internal standard and $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ as solvent. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on solid compounds using Gouy balance at room temperature. Melting points of the ligands and their metal complexes were determined by open capillary method using silicon bath electric melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Mass spectra were recorded on JEOL GCMATE II GC-MS model and analysed in EI mode. Thermal analysis (TGA and DTA) were carried out by using Perkin-Elmer, Diamond TG/DTA. The metal contents of the complexes were determined by ICP-AES technique using Thermo electron IRIS INTERPID II XSP DUO model. The EPR studies were carried out in Bruker EMX Plus model at room temperature. The cyclic voltammetric studies were performed using Versa STAT MC model. *In vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activities were studied at Periyar College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Tiruchirappalli.

Synthesis of ligands :

To an ethanolic solution of sulfapyridine (1.743 g, 0.007 mole), 5-bromo salicylaldehyde (1.407 g, 0.007 mole) in ethanol was added with stirring. The solution was refluxed for 2 h. The precipitate thus formed was cooled to room temperature and washed thoroughly with ethanol and dried (78% yield) (HL^1). The same method was applied to prepare the other ligand which was formed by the condensation of sulfathiazole (1.787 g, 0.007 mole) and 5-bromo salicylaldehyde (1.407 g, 0.007 mole) (74% yield) (HL^2).

Synthesis of metal complexes :

The following general procedure was used in the synthesis of all the complexes. The metal complexes of the

Schiff bases HL^1 (1.299 g, 0.003 mole) and HL^2 (1.314 g, 0.003 mole) were prepared by the addition of a hot solution of the appropriate metal acetates (0.0015 mole) in water to the hot solution of the Schiff base in DMF (5 ml)-ethanol (10 ml) mixture in 1 : 2 molar ratios. The resulting mixture was stirred under reflux for 6–8 h and left for evaporation at room temperature in which coloured solid metal complexes were precipitated. The products were filtered, washed with ethanol and petroleum ether and dried.

Results and discussion

Characterization of the ligands :

The Schiff base ligands (HL^1 , HL^2) were prepared as shown in Scheme 1. The ligands were soluble only in DMF, DMSO and dioxan. The compositions of the ligands were consistent with the microanalytical data. The ^1H NMR spectral data reveal the appearance¹⁵ of the azomethine proton ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}$) signal at 8.91 ppm. This is further supported¹⁶ by the appearance of a band for $\nu(-\text{HC}=\text{N})$ (azomethine) at 1631 and 1562 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of the ligands HL^1 and HL^2 respectively.

Characterization of the metal complexes :

The metal(II) complexes of the ligands (HL^1 and HL^2) were prepared according to the following equation :

where $\text{L} = \text{HL}^1$ and HL^2 , $\text{M} = \text{Co}$, Ni and Cu .

Physical characteristics of the ligands and their complexes are listed in the Table 1.

Conductance and magnetic susceptibility measurements :

The molar conductance values (in DMF) fell within the range 17–35 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for all complexes, show-

Scheme 1. Preparation of ligands.

Table 1. Analytical data of the compounds studied

Sl. no.	Compound/ Molecular formula	Mol. wt.	Yield (%)	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) :					Conductance μ_{eff} (B.M.)	
						Found (Calcd.)					$(\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1})$	(B.M.)
1.	HL ¹ /C ₁₈ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ O ₃ S	432	78	Bright orange	218	49.79 (50.01)	3.18 (3.26)	9.82 (9.72)	6.98 (7.42)	–	–	–
2.	[Co(L ¹) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]/ [Co(C ₃₆ H ₃₀ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₂)]	958	62	Reddish brown	256	44.82 (45.16)	3.18 (3.16)	8.23 (8.76)	7.02 (6.69)	6.23 (6.15)	29.58	4.82
3.	[Ni(L ¹) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]/ [Ni(C ₃₆ H ₃₀ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₂)]	957	58	Light green	280	45.70 (45.17)	3.14 (3.16)	9.05 (8.77)	7.33 (6.69)	6.51 (6.13)	30.40	3.32
4.	[Cu(L ¹) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]/ [Cu(C ₃₆ H ₃₀ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₂)]	962	65	Pale brown	243	45.52 (44.90)	3.28 (3.14)	9.45 (8.73)	5.76 (6.66)	6.49 (6.60)	19.83	1.79
5.	HL ² /C ₁₆ H ₁₂ BrN ₃ O ₃ S ₂	438	74	Yellow	220	43.86 (43.84)	2.73 (2.76)	9.86 (9.58)	13.79 (14.63)	–	–	–
6.	[Co(L ²) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]/ [CoC ₃₂ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄]	970	54	Dark pink	280	40.27 (39.64)	2.78 (2.70)	8.46 (8.66)	13.09 (13.23)	6.42 (6.07)	26.16	4.63
7.	[Ni(L ²) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]/ [NiC ₃₂ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄]	969	50	Pale green	252	40.45 (39.65)	2.82 (2.70)	8.11 (8.67)	13.49 (13.23)	6.19 (6.05)	34.88	2.94
8.	[Cu(L ²) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].H ₂ O/ [CuC ₃₂ H ₂₆ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄]	974	67	Brown	287	40.35 (39.45)	3.11 (2.69)	9.48 (8.63)	13.72 (13.17)	6.61 (6.51)	17.44	1.82

ing their non-electrolytic¹⁷ nature. The observed magnetic moment values 4.63–4.82 B.M. are consistent with half-spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes. The magnetic moment values 1.79–1.82 B.M. measured for the copper(II) complexes lie in the range expected for a d⁹-system, which contains one unpaired electron with octahedral geometry¹⁸. The measured values 2.94–3.32 B.M. for the nickel(II) complexes suggest¹⁹ octahedral geometry for these complexes.

Spectral data :

IR spectra :

The $\nu(\text{HC}=\text{N})$ azomethine band¹⁹ occurs at 1631 cm⁻¹ and 1562 cm⁻¹ in the Schiff base ligands HL¹ and HL² respectively. In the metal(II) complexes there is a shift by 10–20 cm⁻¹ suggesting the involvement of the azomethine nitrogen²⁰ in coordination with the metal(II) ion. This is further confirmed by the appearance of new bands at 450–475 cm⁻¹ due to the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ ²¹ band. The coordination through the phenolic oxygen after deprotonation is revealed by the disappearance of the $\nu(\text{OH})$ phenolic band at 3286–3320 cm⁻¹ and the shift of phenolic $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ ²² band to much lower frequencies 1380–1425 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes. This is further confirmed by the appearance of a new non ligand band at 510–560 cm⁻¹ due to

$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ ²² in all the complexes. The bands in the ligands due to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{SO}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{SO}_2)$ appear at 1357–1386 cm⁻¹ and 1139–1145 cm⁻¹ respectively. These remain unchanged in the complexes, indicating that this group is not involved in coordination²³. This is supported by the unchanged $\nu(\text{S}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ modes appearing at 918–941 cm⁻¹ and 846–856 cm⁻¹ respectively, in the ligands after complexation²⁴. In all the complexes the lattice/coordinated²⁵ water molecules are indicated by the appearance of a broad band in the region 3429–3448 cm⁻¹.

NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectra of the two ligands are given in the Figs. S1 and S2. The formation of Schiff base ligand is revealed by the appearance of the azomethine proton ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$) signal at 8.919 and 8.913 ppm²⁶ in HL¹ and HL² respectively. Both the ligands exhibit signals for aromatic protons, $-\text{NH}$ group and phenolic $-\text{OH}$ group at 6.8 to 8.0, 12.0 to 12.4 and 12.4 to 12.7 ppm respectively²⁷. In ¹³C spectrum of ligands appearance of singlets at 159.2 and 159.8 ppm confirm the presence of azomethine carbon²⁸ and the carbon atoms of aromatic groups were found to be in their expected region.

Electronic spectra :

The absorption spectrum of HL¹ is characterized mainly

Fig. S1. NMR spectrum of HL¹.

Fig. S2. NMR spectrum of HL².

by three absorption bands at 36363 cm^{-1} , 29412 cm^{-1} and 24096 cm^{-1} . The first and second peaks were attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and longer wavelength band at 24096 cm^{-1} is assigned to intra molecular charge transfer of phenolic OH²⁹ respectively. The absorption spectrum of HL² shows four absorption peaks at 39062 cm^{-1} , 37879 cm^{-1} , 34014 cm^{-1} and 29585 cm^{-1} were attributed to intra ligand $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions²⁹. The electronic spectra of cobalt complexes have absorption bands in the regions $10638\text{--}10416\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $24937\text{--}24950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions suggesting octahedral geometry³⁰. The nickel complexes exhibit absorption band in the region $23529\text{--}23810\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the transition ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ indicating octahedral geometry³¹. Electronic spectra of copper complexes display one band in the region of $15748\text{--}15038\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition indicating distorted octahedral geometry around copper ion³².

Mass spectra :

The Schiff base shows (Fig. S8) a molecular ion peak at m/z 432. The molecular ion peak for copper complex (Fig. S9) observed at m/z 962 confirms the stoichiometry of metal chelate as ML₂ type. This composition is also in good agreement with the elemental analysis data. The (M+2) isotopic peak appeared in the ligand confirms the presence of bromine in the structure³³.

EPR studies :

The room temperature EPR spectra of powdered samples of two copper complexes recorded are shown in the Figs. S6 and S7. [Cu(L¹)₂(H₂O)₂] exhibit an isotropic signal, without hyperfine splitting with $g_{\text{iso}} = 2.051$. The g value indicates an increase of the covalent nature of the bonding between the metal ion and the ligand molecule³⁴. The EPR spectra of [Cu(L¹)₂(H₂O)₂].H₂O has asymmetric bands with two 'g' values, $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$. This trend indicates that the complex has a distorted octahedral geometry³⁵.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

The TGA-curve (Fig. S3) of [CuL¹(H₂O)₂] does not show any considerable weight loss up to $140\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Thereafter, it starts losing weight and the first weight loss is completed at $190\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is observed to be 3.62% against theoretical weight loss of 3.74% . This weight loss confirms the presence of two coordinated water molecules in the complex³⁶. At $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ a sudden weight loss was observed which seems to be completed at $660\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (ob-

served weight loss = 87.9% , calculated weight loss 88.4%). This weight loss corresponds to the elimination of two molecules of L¹ (ligand). Finally it attains a constant composition corresponding to copper oxide at $700\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Observed 9.06% and theoretically retained mass = 8.3%).

The thermogram (Fig. S4) of [Ni(L²)₂(H₂O)₂] shows a considerable weight loss of 3.8% (theoretical weight loss 3.74%) at $190\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which corresponds to the elimination of two coordinated water molecules³⁶. The second weight loss is noticed in the temperature range $360\text{--}710\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (observed weight loss = 88.4% , calculated weight loss = 88.5%). This weight loss corresponds to the elimination of two molecules of L² (ligand). Thereafter it attains a constant composition corresponding to nickel oxide (Observed retained mass = 8.18% , theoretical retained mass 7.7%).

[Cu(L²)₂(H₂O)₂].H₂O (Fig. S5) lost one molecule of lattice water³⁷ in the temperature range $105\text{--}115\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the weight loss observed is 1.7% (calculated 1.9%). The second weight loss was noticed in the temperature range $120\text{--}150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The corresponding weight loss observed 3.86% (calculated 3.69%) is consistent with the elimination of two coordinated water molecules³⁶. The third weight loss is in the temperature range of $280\text{--}670\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (observed 86.20% , calculated 88.1%) is due to the decomposition of two molecules of ligand (L²). The weight loss continues beyond this temperature and finally attains a constant mass corresponding to copper oxide (observed 10.0% , calculated 8.17%).

Fig. S3. TGA curve of [Cu(L¹)₂(H₂O)₂].

Fig. S4. TGA curve of $[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$.

Fig. S5. TGA curve of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Cyclic voltammetric studies :

Cyclic voltammograms of complexes in the concentration of $10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ in DMF were recorded in an electrochemical cell, equipped with a Pt, Ag/AgCl and glassy carbon (GC) as counter, reference, and working electrode respectively. Tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) was used as supporting electrolyte. Electrochemical cyclic voltammetry measurements were performed at room temperature and over a potential range between -2.3 V to $+1.0 \text{ V}$ for the complex $[\text{Co}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$. The cyclic voltammogram (Fig. S10) exhibits a reduction peak at $E_{pc} = 0.514 \text{ V}$ and an oxidation peak at $E_{pa} = -1.260 \text{ V}$ corresponding to $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}/\text{Co}^{\text{III}}$ redox couple³⁸.

Fig. S6. EPR spectrum of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$.

Fig. S7. EPR spectrum of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Antimicrobial activity :

Disc diffusion technique has been used for determining the activity of Schiff base ligands and their complexes against bacterial species and fungi. It is clear from the biological data that the ligands (Figs. S11 and S12) and complexes have significant antimicrobial activities against the pathogenic bacteria. The results compared with standard drug (ciprofloxacin $5 \mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$ for bacteria, Nystatin $100 \text{ units}/\text{disc}$ for fungi) have indicated that complexes were active but activity was lesser than the standard drugs. The results thus obtained are explained on the basis of

Fig. S8. Mass spectrum of HL¹.

Fig. S9. Mass spectrum of [Cu(L¹)₂(H₂O)₂].

Fig. S10. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{Co}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$.

Fig. S11. Biological activity of the ligand HL^2 and its nickel and copper complexes against *S. aureus*.

Fig. S12. Biological activity of the ligand HL^1 and its cobalt complex against *Candida albicans*.

Overtone's concept and Chelation theory³⁹. Comparisons of the biological activity of the synthesized compounds are presented in Tables 2 and 3. The free Schiff base ligands and some of their complexes exhibit better activity. Remarkable enhancement is observed for $[\text{Co}(\text{L}^1)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L}^2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ complexes. All the compounds have shown variable average inhibition activity against different strains. The activity decreases in the case of nickel complexes compared to ligand. In specific the cobalt and copper complexes of the ligands show very high activity against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*. The overall activities of the ligands have been enhanced after chelation and thus the biological activity increases on complexation.

Conclusion

In this work two new Schiff bases, HL^1 and HL^2 and their metal complexes with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal ions are synthesized. The two Schiff base ligands coordinated to the metal ions in a bidentate manner with N, O donor sites of the azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen. The metal ligand stoichiometry in all these complexes is 1 : 2. Mass spectra are in agreement with elemental analysis, confirming the composition of the ligand and its complex. All the complexes are non-electrolytic in nature. Thermal studies explored the presence of lattice/coordinated water in the complexes. On the basis of the above discussions, it is concluded that all the complexes exhibit

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of HL¹ and its complexes

Compd.	Gram +ve		Gram -ve		Fungi	
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>	<i>Mucor sp.</i>
HL ¹	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
[Co(L ¹) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	++++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
[Ni(L ¹) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	+++	+++	+++	+++	++++	+++
[Cu(L ¹) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	+++	+++	++	+++	+++	+++

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity of HL² and its complexes

Compd.	Gram +ve		Gram -ve		Fungi	
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Klebsiella sp.</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>
HL ²	++++	+++	++++	++++	+++	++
[Co(L ²) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	+++	++	+++	+++	+++	+++
[Ni(L ²) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	+++	+++	+++	++++	+++	+++
[Cu(L ²) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	++++	+++	++	+++	+++	++++

Inhibition zone measured in diameters : (+) for 6–10 mm, (++) for 10–14 mm, (+++) for 14–20 mm, (++++) for > 20 mm.

six-coordinated octahedral geometry as shown in the Fig. 1. Additionally some metal complexes possess anti-bacterial and antifungal activity against the selected species of bacteria or fungi more than the free Schiff base ligands which is in accordance with the fact that the chelation of metal to ligands increase the microbial activity of the molecule. The outcome of the study is that cobalt complexes of both the ligands are observed to be the most active against all bacterial strains.

Fig. 1. Structure of metal complex.

where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}

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